

Studies on Adsorption of Cetyl Trimethylammonium Bromide on Xylene Globules Dispersed in Water

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The role of stabiliser concentration on the lowering of interfacial tension of xylene/water system has been determined and from the data obtained, the amount of stabiliser adsorbed per unit area of the surface has been calculated, using the Gibbs equation.

The electrophoretic mobility of the oil globules has also been measured at several concentrations of the stabiliser and using these data the values of zeta-potential have been calculated with a view to ascertaining its dependence on the number of stabiliser ions adsorbed per unit area on the surface.

The role of stabiliser concentration on the lowering of surface tension of xylene—water system has been studied and the amount of the stabiliser adsorbed per unit area of the surface has been calculated according to the Gibbs equation.

EXPERIMENTAL

A xylene/water emulsion was prepared by using cetyl trimethylammonium bromide, previously purified by repeated recrystallisation from ethanol. *m*-Xylene (b.p. 139.1°) was redistilled and double-distilled water was used in these experiments. An excess of HCl was added to the aqueous solution of the stabiliser to suppress hydrolysis as well as to maintain a constant ionic strength. Solutions of three different ionic strengths containing HCl and cetyl trimethylammonium bromide were prepared, the concentration of cetyl trimethylammonium bromide varying from $0.55 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $35.11 \times 10^{-3} M$, i.e. about 70 times.

Measurement of Interfacial Tension (γ) and Estimation of Adsorption

Because of the simplicity of the apparatus and the ease of manipulation, the method of Miller and Bartell¹ was employed for the measurement of interfacial tension. The values of interfacial tension, measured for all the three solutions having different ionic strengths, are recorded in Table I (A—C).

The surface excess, Γ , was calculated using the Gibbs equation:

$$\Gamma = -C/RT \cdot d\gamma/dC,$$

the values of $d\gamma/dC$ being obtained from the graphical plot of interfacial tension against concentration, taking R as 8.3×10^7 erg/degree and T as 298°. These data are also recorded in Table I (A—C). The gradual decrease in interfacial tension with the increase in concentration of the stabiliser indicates adsorption of the stabilising ion at the interface.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that the values of Γ at first increases and then becomes constant at about 4×10^{-10} g. ion/cm².

TABLE I

Concn. of stabiliser soln. ($C \times 10^3 M$).	Concn. of HCl soln. ($C \times 10^2 M$).	Interfacial tension (dynes/cm).	Γ (calc. from Gibbs eq. in $g./cm^2 \times 10^{10}$).
A. Ionic strength = 0.0025.			
0.550	0.2495	33.50	3.00
1.097	0.2480	29.50	3.30
2.195	0.2478	23.10	3.78
4.390	0.2450	16.50	3.89
8.780	0.2412	9.50	4.00
17.560	0.2324	4.90	
B. Ionic strength = 0.005.			
0.550	0.4995	33.00	3.00
1.097	0.4980	28.50	3.30
2.195	0.4978	22.10	3.67
6.58	0.4924	11.60	4.00
17.56	0.4825	1.80	
C. Ionic strength = 0.01.			
0.550	0.9995	29.36	..
1.097	0.9980	25.50	3.4
2.195	0.9978	19.10	3.8
4.390	0.9958	12.60	4.2
8.780	0.9912	6.02	..
35.110	0.9840	1.85	

Measurement of Electrophoretic Mobility

Phillips and Haydon² measured the zeta-potential of the oil droplets (the oil being petroleum, b.p. > 120°), stabilised by a number of cationic and anionic detergents, with a view to ascertaining a relationship between surface-charge density and this potential.

Chattoraj and Bull³ investigated the electrophoretic behaviour of nujol particles, stabilised by octadecylamines and sodium dodecyl sulphate. Haydon and Phillips⁴ studied the relationship between the bulk concentration and the amount adsorbed at oil/water interface for dodecyl trimethylammonium bromide and sodium lauryl sulphate. The variation of ζ -potential and Ψ_0 with increasing concentration of surfactant has been discussed by Haydon⁵. Lyklema and Overbeek⁶ have discussed the possibility of variation of η in the electrical double layer. Alexander and Hunter⁷, however, think on the basis of the experimental data of Haydon that the electroviscous effect will be negligibly small in the diffuse part of the double layer.

2. *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, 18, 194.

3. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, 63, 1809.

4. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 54, 698.

5. "Recent Progress in Surface Science", Vol. 1, 1964.

6. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1961, 16, 501.

7. *ibid.*, 1963, 18, 820.

In the present investigation, the electrophoretic mobility of the globules of xylene/water emulsion, stabilised by cetyl trimethylammonium bromide, was measured by the microcataphoretic method. The procedure adopted was the same as that described by Chakraborty and Ghosh⁸. The emulsions used were of two ionic strengths, viz., 0.0025 and 0.01. For each concentration of the stabiliser, the mobility (U) of a fairly large number of globules was measured and their average was taken. From these data the values of ζ -potential were also calculated by using the equation:

$$\zeta = \frac{4 \pi \eta}{D} \times U \times (300)^2.$$

The data are recorded in Table II (A and B).

TABLE II

Concn. of stabiliser soln. ($C \times 10^3 M$).	Log C .	Average electrophoretic mobility (U) (cm/sec/volt/cm) ($U \times 10^4$).	Calc. ζ -potential.
A. Ionic strength = 0.0025			
0.550		9.06	129.9 mv
1.007		10.14	131.1
2.165		10.27	132.8
4.300		10.58	136.9
8.780		10.80	140.8
17.560		11.67	150.9
B. Ionic strength = 0.01			
0.550	$\bar{6}.74$	9.02	116.3
1.007	$\bar{5}.04$	9.34	120.8
2.165	$\bar{5}.34$	9.60	124.2
4.300	$\bar{5}.64$	10.10	130.8
8.780	$\bar{5}.94$	10.50	136.9
35.110	$\bar{4}.64$	10.81	139.8

DISCUSSION

Data recorded in Table II(A and B) show that the electrophoretic mobility increases from 9.06 to 11.67×10^{-4} cm/sec/volt/cm as the concentration of the stabiliser increases from $0.55 \times 10^{-3} M$ to $17.56 \times 10^{-3} M$ for emulsions having ionic strength 0.0025. For emulsions of ionic strength 0.01 also, an increase of mobility with increasing concentration occurs.

In Fig. 1 the values of U have been plotted against I , i.e., the amount of stabiliser adsorbed per cm². It will be noticed that within the range investigated, the relation is linear. It should also be noted that as the ionic strength increases from 0.0025 to 0.01, the electrophoretic mobility decreases appreciably.

8. This Journal, 1963, 40, 425.

Incidentally, for ionic strength 0.0025, the ζ -potential increases from 128.8 mv to 150.9 mv only, whereas the concentration of the stabiliser changes from $0.55 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $17.56 \times 10^{-5} M$. Similarly for ionic strength 0.01, the ζ -potential increases from 116.3 mv to 139.8 mv with the increase in the concentration of the stabiliser from $0.55 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $35.1 \times 10^{-5} M$. It is thus evident that the rate of increase of ζ -potential with the increase of concentration of the stabiliser is quite small. Finally, the ζ -potential has been plotted against $\log C$ (vide Fig. 2) at ionic strength of 0.01. It is found to be linear in nature. The slope of the line is 16.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

It has been shown by Ghosh⁹ that in the case of glass surface, variation of ζ with C can be represented by the equation :

$$\zeta = \frac{RT}{(1+P)F} \log C$$

where $1+P = \phi_0/\zeta$. When the ionic strength is not too small, P appears to remain constant although the concentration of the surfactant ion increases. If P is put equal to 2.7, the slope according to this equation should be 16, as stated above.

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